

RoguePlots_UBI_24_TE-linked-noparasitic: This pdf contains the RoguePlots created for the 24 fossils resulting from the unconstrained Bayesian analysis for 24 fossils using total evidence data, excluding parasitic taxa, and linking branch lengths across partitions (UBI-24-TE).

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X_Archaeanthus_linnenbergeri

PP

X_Archaestella_verticillatus

PP

X_Bertilanthus_scanicus

PP

X_Canrightia_resinifera

PP

X_Carpestella_lacunata

PP

X_Cecilanthus_polymerus

PP

X_Chloranthistemon_endressii

PP

X_Dakotanthus_cordiformis

PP

X_Divisestylus_brevistamineus

PP

X_Florissantia_quilchenensis

PP

X_Kajanthus_lusitanicus

PP

X_Mabelia_connatifila

PP

X_Mauldinia_mirabilis

PP

X_Microvictoria_svitkoana

PP

X_Paleoclusia_chevalieri

PP

X_Paradinandra_suecica

PP

X_Pentapetalum_trifasciculandricus

PP

X *Platydiscus peltatus*

PP

X_Quadriplatanus_georgianus

PP

X_Rariglanda_jerseyensis

PP

X_Saururus_tuckerae

PP

X_Spanomera_mauldinensis

PP

X_Tylerianthus_crossmanensis

PP

X_Virginianthus_calycanthoides

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